

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES IN YOUNG CHILDREN IN LITERARY READING LESSONS

Akhmedova Mahfuza Sadykovna

Scientific supervisor. Associate Professor of Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizami.
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.

Email: maxfuzasadikovna@mail.ru

Mingboeva Mokhina Tulkinjon kizi

student, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.

Email: mokhinamingboyeva20@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This article examines aspects of the development of new abilities of students in reading lessons. Reading lessons are considered as a way to develop creative abilities in children of primary school age, and exemplary techniques and methods of work in a literary reading lesson are also presented.*

Keywords: *literary reading, creativity, ability, development of creative abilities, methods, literary reading lesson, relevance, techniques, activation.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ У ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ВОЗРАСТА НА УРОКАХ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОГО ЧТЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются аспекты развития новых способностей учащихся на уроках чтения. Уроки чтения рассматриваются как способ развития творческих способностей у детей младшего школьного возраста, а также представлены примерные приемы и методы работы на уроке литературного чтения.*

Ключевые слова: *литературное чтение, творчество, способности, развитие творческих способностей, методы, урок литературного чтения, актуальность, приемы, активизация.*

Currently, the issue of developing creative abilities is very relevant. In the large dictionary of psychology, creativity is interpreted as “practical or theoretical human activity in which new results arise (knowledge, decisions, methods of action, material products), at least in the subject of the activity.” Creativity has a huge impact on individuals and society as a whole. By engaging

in creative activity, a person goes beyond the ordinary, increases the level of his intelligence, develops thinking, imagination and other higher mental functions.

All cultural values created by man are the result of creative activity. Creative people are in demand and always find ways to realize their creative potential. Life in the era of the development of science and technology requires us to think flexibly and new approaches to solving problems. It is no secret that in many professions, the activities performed are transferred to machines, and people are an integral part of the intelligence, so they need to activate their creativity by adequately responding to innovations. Therefore, the development of creative potential is the most important task of a modern school.

Literary reading is one of the main subjects of primary education. Education not only contributes to the overall development and upbringing of the child, but also ensures the effectiveness of teaching other subjects, therefore the study of this discipline is aimed at achieving one of the goals: the development of artistic, creative and cognitive abilities.

The development of the creative abilities of younger schoolchildren is successfully realized through literary reading classes in the process of studying literary works. At the same time, teachers use creative reading methods, which, through various types of activities, contribute to the development of observation, the ability to see and hear the phenomena of life, the ability to find the right words and expressions to convey their impressions

These methods are very rich in interesting techniques that are most specific to reading literature. Not only does this promote children's creativity, but most importantly, it develops children's reading skills and awakens empathy in them.

Literary reading classes - creative activity of students, based on the study of literary works, consists of reading by roles, drawing pictures with words, studying various ways of handling transformed texts, finding literary works. The lesson is aimed not only at developing general academic skills in reading and working with text. However, classes are also aimed at developing artistic, creative and cognitive abilities, as well as emotional responsiveness when reading works of fiction. Reading literature develops artistic and creative abilities, the ability to create your own texts based on works of art and the ability to reproduce paintings and illustrations by artists based on experience.

Expressive reading plays a leading role in the development of creative abilities. By developing reading skills, children not only learn to read texts out loud consciously and expressively, but also participate in the process of analysis, summarize the results of the analysis, and practically implement their understanding and interpretation of the work. Divide the text into

meaningful parts, give them titles, and then find passages from the text as directed by your teacher or to support your own ideas. Gradually move from general reading to role-playing reading.

The next method for developing children's creativity is retelling, creative adaptation, since during it the child's personal attitude to the work and his own style of storytelling are revealed.

Read by role. More complex forms of role-playing involve analysis of the character's emotional state and personality.

In primary school we use role-playing reading to read stories, fairy tales, legends and epics that contain dialogue.

I write fairy tales and riddles. Solving riddles plays a huge role in the development of children's imagination, intelligence and logical thinking. By guessing or writing down riddles, children not only learn to identify the signs or actions of specific objects, but also master vivid, figurative speech.

A fairy tale for a child is a world of fantasies, dreams and expectations of miracles, so a child loves to listen to it from childhood and his first ideas about life are associated with it. When developing primary school students' creativity when it comes to writing stories, teachers usually gradually introduce children to the role of the storyteller.

Thus, we can conclude that in each literary reading lesson it is possible to develop the creative abilities of students using different methods and techniques. Since the development of creative abilities is based on the development of higher mental functions, classes will become more interesting and the quality of learning will improve. Children are motivated to read books and participate more actively in activities.

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